

I NO LONGER CARRY CASH FOR PAYMENTS: EXAMINING MILLENNIALS INTENTION TO USE MOBILE WALLETS

Ankita Sharma

Research Associate, IMT, Ghaziabad.

Corresponding Author Orcid Id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2321-8403>

Dr. Shalini Rahul Tiwari

Associate Professor, IMT, Ghaziabad.

Gurmeet Singh

Associate Professor, GLS University, Ahmedabad.

Abstract

Purpose - The present study attempts to evaluate millennials' attitudes and usage intentions towards mobile wallets, specifically from an emerging country perspective. Using the UTAUT theory, this study elaborates upon the significance of technological anxiety, effort expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions and rewards on consumers' attitude towards mobile wallet which will lead to consumers' intention to use mobile wallet. **Design/ Methodology/ approach** - To understand the relationships between the proposed variables, partial least square structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) were adopted. **Findings** - The findings revealed that rewards, social influence, facilitating condition and effort expectancy had a significant impact on attitude towards mobile wallets. While technological anxiety had no significant impact on millennial users' attitude towards mobile wallets, findings posited that there was a significant impact of attitude towards mobile wallets and millennial users' intention to use them. **Originality/Value** – The study is from the emerging economy context. The study integrates the UTAUT model with the rewards as an important variable. The findings consequentially contribute to the scarce literature on mobile wallet adoption by (a) focusing on a user cohort that has extensively adapted to the phenomenon of using mobile wallets yet has scant academic understanding, (b) extending the research questions to understand the aspect of rewards through cashback and e-coupons as potential motivators behind using mobile wallets and , (c) suggesting insights through which policymakers and brands may develop effective programs to attract millennial users.

Keywords: *Mobile wallets, rewards, attitude towards mobile wallets, technological anxiety, millennials, UTAUT.*

Paper type - Research paper

INTRODUCTION

Data affordances and democratization of the internet have significantly changed the way consumers make online purchase decisions (Hearn, 2020; Adeola *et al.*, 2021) Though mobile payment services (MPS) has existed since the beginning of the internet (Jebarajakirthy and Shankar, 2021; Kaur *et al.*, 2020), mobile wallets are newest innovation in the area that has made a global presence (Alalwan *et al.*, 2016, 2017; George and Sunny, 2021; Shaw and Eschenbrenner, 2021). Covid-19 has led to an exponential increase in the usage of mobile wallets (Al-Dmour *et al.*, 2021; Brem *et al.*, 2021; Chawla and Joshi, 2021; Daragme *et al.*, 2021; Kumar *et al.*, 2022). Existing studies on mobile wallets have focused on convenience factor of mobile wallet among consumers (Chawla and Joshi, 2021; Garrouch, 2021; Phuong *et al.*, 2020; Talwar *et al.*, 2021; Yan

et al., 2021). However, there are few studies that have studied the adoption behavior (Lew *et al.*, 2020; Mombeuil, 2020). Since consumers spending behavior in technology adoption is none standardized, it is critical to examine this phenomenon in different contexts. Such as an emerging market context in India is important for study since it has the highest young population in the world and expected a GDP growth of around 7.4% in 2022-23 (FICCI economic outlook survey, 2022). Millennials make up 34% of India's total population thus exhibit a high online spending that is critical to the country's economic growth, as their portion of the wallet grows (Sharma, 2021)).

However, millennials being tech-savvy they prefer ease of use and convenience in their purchase options thus preferring digital payments via phone using QR codes or UPI. Because of their inherent affinity for technology, they gravitate toward brands that provide a variety of payment alternatives (Bhatia, 2020). During COVID-19, their tendency to pay using technology increased significantly. As per the report, 39% of millennials preferred to pay in-store with contactless cards or digital wallets during the epidemic, indicating that they valued safety (Global payment, 2022).

Another interesting aspect of online payment are the rewards earned; almost 64% of millennials prefer online payment methods due to rewards offered by the suppliers (FIS Global, 2021; Glasheen, 2019). Therefore, it becomes important to study rewards as a construct to understand the adoption behavior of mobile wallets. Besides factors such as technological anxiety, efforts expectancy, social influence and facilitating conditions need to be studied with respect to the attitude and intention of millennials towards mobile wallets. The study poses the following research questions: -

- What are the factors responsible for millennials' intention to adopt mobile wallets?
- Does technological anxiety and rewards influence the attitude towards mobile wallets?
- Does attitude significantly influence the consumers' intention to use mobile wallets?

The current study is unique in four ways: firstly, the study uses the UTAUT model to analyze the research questions and it has been extended by adding new constructs, namely, rewards and technological anxiety, secondly, this study has been conducted among millennials in an emerging nation like India (de Albuquerque *et al.*, 2016). Prior studies have examined technological fear or anxiety among users of mobile wallets and the results were negative. Our study has re-examined this construct in the post-covid scenario. Lastly, reward as a construct has been examined as an influencer on the relationship between attitude and consumers' intention to use mobile wallets.

This manuscript is divided into four sections; the first consists of a literature review coercing the theoretical foundations, the relationship among the constructs leading to a derived model. In the second part, methodology is discussed in detail coercing the development of a questionnaire, data collection and validation of hypotheses. The next section consists of SEM analysis and validity of the hypotheses. The last section reviews and discusses the findings of the study and the conclusion to direction for future research.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical foundation

Numerous studies have employed different information systems or technology models to study the individual's acceptance and use of technology. Earlier studies have employed the technology acceptance model (TAM) for understanding the users' acceptance of technology. TAM has been extended, adapted and

adopted in various context to understand users' behavior. TAM was being used alongside innovation diffusion theory (IDT) to understand the adoption behavior of mobile payment services and value added services (Augsburg and Hedman, 2014). Though TAM being the most popular model to study the mobile payment services, still it has been criticized for providing generic information on individual's opinion and acceptance of new technologies.

In order to address the limitations of TAM, Venkatesh *et al.*, (2003) opined Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT). While the preceding theories only explained 30-40% of the diversity in adoption behaviour, UTAUT is said to be superior, since it can account for 70% of it (Venkatesh *et al.*, 2003). Being a comprehensive model, UTAUT became the second most popular model to be used to examine a variety of adoption behaviors (Patil *et al.*, 2017). Existing literature has established the theory of UTAUT to be a valid technique for predicting adoption in a variety of technology-based systems across a range of applications (Tarhini *et al.*, 2016). Derived from the UTAUT model, there is a proposed model in figure 1 with appropriate hypotheses. In this study, authors tried to examine the impact of some critical variables such as the effort expectancy, technological anxiety, social influence, facilitating condition and rewards on the adoption of mobile wallets. <Insert figure 1>

Technological Anxiety (TA)

(Featherman and Pavlou, 2003) stated that consumers' perception of risk affects their intention to use mobile services. It may also be noted herein that technology can directly increase the consumers' anxiety. Thus, their attitude is often influenced by their level of anxiety (Meuter *et al.*, 2003; Venkatesh, 2000). Similarly, Parasuraman (2000) opined that use of technology has benefited consumers, but it has also fostered a certain level of frustration among them, which in turn, often goes on to impact their attitude towards the intention to use technology (Mukerjee *et al.*, 2020; Park *et al.*, 2019). It may therefore be proposed that TA negatively influences consumers' attitudes toward technology usage (Baccarella *et al.*, 2020; Liljander *et al.*, 2006). The same narrative was further supported by Park *et al.*, (2019) and Mukerjee *et al.*, (2020), adding that the discomfort is actually caused while using a technology per se. Meuter *et al.*, (2003), suggested that within the ambit of a retail environment, TA serves as an important construct to determine the consumers' intent to use. When first confronted with new technologies, TA is an apprehensive notion that describes the individual's attitude and intention to adapt (Venkatesh and Bala, 2008; Verkasalo *et al.*, 2010). On the other hand, consumers' adoption of self-service technology (SST) is lowered as a result of TA; they are concerned about their first experience with modern technologies, which has a negative impact on their intent to use it (Gelbrich and Sattler, 2014). Demoulin and Djelassi, (2016) and Chen and Chang, (2013) found that TA negatively influences the consumers' acceptance of SST, and adoption of new technologies thereof, like in the case of automated personal shopping assistance. Technological anxiety (TA) thereby poses to be a critical construct in defining the individuals' attitude toward using m-wallets. Based on the discussion so far, we hypothesize that: -

H₁: TA negatively influences the consumer's ATMW

Effort Expectancy (EE)

Effort Expectancy (EE) is a term that describes the ease with which people use technology (Venkatesh *et al.*, 2003). Researchers have found both significant and non-significant influence of EE on attitudes and behavioural intentions (BI) of users towards use of technology. Researchers (e.g. Schierz *et al.*, 2010; Bailey *et al.*, 2017; Wulandari, 2017; Tussyah *et al.*, 2021) have shown that EE does have a significant influence on consumers' attitudes towards m-wallets. Even though a large section of the Indian populous owns a

smartphone, the country's m-wallet adoption is still in its infancy (Kumar *et al.*, 2022; Shaw *et al.*, 2022). There are other studies in mobile payment services domain where scholars found insignificant influence of EE on intention to use (Alam *et al.*, 2020; Madan and Yadav, 2016; Susanto *et al.*, 2020; Venkatesh *et al.*, 2003). In such a situation, it becomes necessary to understand the influence of EE on attitude toward mobile wallets and hence following hypothesis can be formulated: -

H₂: EE positively influences the consumer's ATMW.

Social Influence (SI)

A person's choice to use technology is influenced by other people in his/her life that is referred to as "social influence" (Venkatesh *et al.*, 2003). Scholars have found both significant and insignificant influence on the intention to use a technology. As per the past studies it can be seen that SI does have a significant influence on the attitude towards technology like mobile payment ecosystem (Thakur and Srivastava, 2014; Boon *et al.*, 2021; Mater *et al.*, 2021; Sukwadi *et al.*, 2022). A research in Cambodia also validated that SI has a significant influence on the intention to use mobile payment services (Do *et al.*, 2019). However, few studies have found an insignificant influence on the intention to use mobile wallets (Malik *et al.*, 2019; Upadhyay *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, there is a need to study this from the emerging economy perspective and hence we posit the following hypothesis:

H₃: SI positively influences the consumers' ATMW.

Facilitating Condition (FC)

Facilitating conditions (FC) relate to a consumer's belief in the resources that are accessible to him/her and which help him/her engage in a specific behaviour (Venkatesh *et al.*, 2003). Prior studies suggest that a person's behavioral desire to utilise mobile wallets rises if the operational infrastructure is in place (Gupta *et al.*, 2018; Musleh *et al.*, 2015; Oliveira *et al.*, 2016; Tandon and Kiran, 2018; Zhong *et al.*, 2021). A few other studies on the adoption of m-wallets have found that FC does influence BI positively in terms of consumers' usage of m-wallets (Morosan and DeFranco, 2016; Sivathanu, 2019; Soodan and Rana, 2020). Interestingly, some studies have found no relation between FC and behavioral intention in terms of m-wallet usage and adoption (Musleh *et al.*, 2015; Oliveira *et al.*, 2016; Gupta *et al.*, 2018; Tandon and Kiran, 2018; Zhong *et al.*, 2021). Since the result of the above mentioned studies has been inconclusive, we hypothesize that:

H₄: FC will positively influence the consumer's ATMW.

Rewards

Rewards such as gifts, incentives, cashbacks, coupons, etc. are extrinsic motivator that causes the achievement of certain behaviour (Davis *et al.*, 1992); such as motivating the consumer to use a product or services. (Varnali *et al.*, 2012) proposed that individuals are willing to put extra effort if extrinsic motivation is attached. Along similar lines, Kim and Han, (2014) also opined that consumers could make extra efforts to acquire these rewards. They further reinstated that in the marketing ecosystem, if the advertising message includes benefits, the consumers' focus tends to increase. Past studies have also shown that in the long-run extrinsic motivation are, in effect, internalised (Deci *et al.*, 1991; Ryan and Deci, 2000; Vallerand, 1997). Ryan and Connell, (1989) had earlier proposed that through rewards, a consumer's external behaviour can be regulated internally. In the context of m-wallets, companies often offer cashback, value-added services, coupons and discounts to lure consumers, which in turn, lead to a positive attitude towards adopting m-wallet (George and Sunny, 2021; Isa *et al.*, 2021). Through this lens, it is important to study the rewards construct

vis a vis its impact on consumers' ATMW. Hence, we posit:

H₅: Rewards positively influence the consumers' ATMW.

Attitude towards Mobile Wallets (ATMW)

The “degree to which customers have a positive or negative opinion about the behaviour” in question is referred to as attitude (Ajzen, 1991). Several well-known theories have made use of the framework related to technology like TAM (Davis, 1989) and TRA (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1975). Despite the fact that attitude played a significant part, the final UTAUT model did not include it. Several studies have discovered a positive link between attitude and BI when studied in a mobile payment environment (Wulandari, 2017; Dwivedi *et al.*, 2019; Shaikh *et al.*, 2021). For instance, Schierz *et al.*, (2010) conducted a study in Germany and found that both consumers' attitudes and BI to use m-wallets have an intrinsic and significant relationship. As a result, it is safe to say that ATMW adoption should be taken into account as part of a research. Hence, we posit:

H₆: ATMW positively influences consumers' intention to use m-wallets

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sample

A descriptive design technique was used, for which an online structured survey was designed to collect data through Google forms; administered through online mediums, like survey monkey, emails, Facebook and WhatsApp. Importantly, the participants chose to participate in the survey voluntarily and were not persuaded in any way. They were given ample time to complete it.

Purposive sampling was used to collect data. Two screening questions were used to identify the target respondents: ‘do you use m-wallet?’ and whether your age was between 25-40 years! Participants were not permitted to participate in the survey if they failed to pass the filter questions. Data was collected during January 2021 to April 2021; the total sample size consisted of 348 participants. Of the total survey forms 28 were rejected due to incomplete information, giving a total of 320 forms. Further, the sample consisted of 53% men, 45% women and 2% transgender. All of the respondents belonged to millennials, meaning they were born between 1981 and 1995. In terms of their educational qualification, 61% were graduates, 35 % were post-graduates, and 4% were other. In terms of occupation, 17% were in business, 11% in government service, 9% homemakers, and 63% in private companies. Some of the earlier studies too had a similar size (Leong *et al.*, 2020; Thakur, 2013).

Measures, Validity, and Statistical Tools

A five-point Likert scale which ranged from “strongly agree (5)” to “strongly disagree (1)” was used to gauge the intention of users. The scales for measuring the variables were adapted from the previous studies such as the scale for ATMW from Ajzen (1991); for consumers' intention to use m-wallets scale from Venkatesh *et al.*, (2003) was used.

For testing face validity, the draft of the questionnaire was shown to 3 ‘academic experts’ and two m-wallet companies' marketing managers. Based on their feedback, some minor modifications were made in phrasing the questions in order to make them more understandable. In the final questionnaire, demographics details, 28 items, along with two filter questions, were added. We analysed the data with the help of MS-Excel, SPSS and Smart-PLS.

DATA ANALYSIS

Measurement Model and Validity

The software Smartpls 3.0 was used for conducting the data analysis (Ringle *et al.*, 2015). Notably, when the test size isn't huge, and the interconnection between variables is complicated, partial least square may be used (Hair *et al.*, 2014). PLS in fact, effectively manages data that consist of both formative and reflective indicators of the construct, unlike AMOS (Dellande *et al.*, 2004). In our study, all the constructs measuring the second-order construct (ATMW) were treated as formative measures as seen in figure 1. All the variables, namely TA, SI, EE, along with the FC and rewards, were noted to be distinct and important for studying the second-order construct (i.e. ATMW). <Insert figure 1>

Inner Model Assessment and Common Method Bias

Furthermore, Cronbach alpha, composite reliability (CR) and indicator reliability tests were used to measure the reliability of the questionnaire. All the variables were accepted since the *rho* value was greater than 0.70 (Nunally and Bernstein, 1978). Moreover, the square loading of all the variables was above 0.40, assuring the internal reliability of the variable (Wong, 2013). Additionally, the CR of all the constructs was above 0.70 (Hair *et al.*, 2014). Table I shows the CR values for each construct. <Insert table I>

Then the validity of the scale was tested and the average variance extracted (AVE) score were noted. The AVE was above 0.50 for all the constructs, and therefore it was considered to be valid (Wong, 2013). Table II contains the AVEs for each construct. Then, the Heterotraitmonotrait (HTMT) ratio test was used to check the discriminant validity of the constructs; table II shows these values. The values of HTMT constructs should be lower than 0.90 (Henseler *et al.*, 2016); HTMT ratios were found to be lower than 0.85 in Table II, hence establishing discriminant validity for our study. <Insert table II>

Structural Model Measurement

The bootstrapping was used to test the structural model in PLS-SEM since PLS-SEM is regarded as a "nonparametric method" (Hair *et al.*, 2019). Table III shows the outcomes created from bootstrapping. <Insert table III>

Collinearity and Path Coefficients

Table III shows the results after bootstrapping with significance testing. Herein, it may be noted that ATMW does show a strong impact on a consumer's intention to use it. It was interesting to note that insignificant impact of technological anxiety (TA) was found on ATMW. As noted from Table III that the relationship between EE, SI, FC and rewards with ATMW was also found to be significant. Moreover, the VIF values are below 5, alluding to the fact that the study has no issues of multi-collinearity (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

In-sample prediction

In PLS-SEM, we used the R² value (see table IV) to assess the in-sample predictive power (Hair *et al.*, 2019; Rigdon, 2012). Based upon these criteria, the value of R² for consumers' intention to use m-wallets was noted to be 0.672; while for ATMW, it was 0.44; this indicates moderate in-sample explanatory power (Henseler *et al.*, 2009; Hair *et al.*, 2011). <Insert table IV>

Out-of-sample prediction

According to Shmueli *et al.*, (2016), out-of-sample prediction is critical to assessing the model's robustness. In this study, PLSpredict 10 folds were applied to know the predictive performance of the endogenous

constructs of ATMW and consumers' intention to use m-wallets. Table V shows the PLSpredict results obtained after 10 folds. Firstly, we assessed the "root mean squared error" (RMSE) for all the endogenous variables (ATMW and consumers' intention to mobile wallets) (as shown in figure 2. Further, as per Table V, it is clear that all the Q^2_{predict} values were above 0, and hence all the endogenous variables were above the benchmarks. After this, we compared the RMSE values with the LM RMSE values in PLSpredict. It has been opined by Hair *et al.*, (2019) that when the RMSE values of all indicators (minority or the same numbers) in the PLS-SEM provide lower values when compared to the naïve LM benchmark, it suggests medium predictive potential. <Insert table V> < Insert figure 2>

DISCUSSION

Due to the expansion of mobile technology, mobile payment systems (MPS) has gained both in relevance and importance, as it offers convenience, ubiquity and saves time (Baptista and Oliveira, 2015; Mu and Lee, 2022; Oliveira *et al.*, 2014). However, it is not easily accepted by Indian consumers as a payment method (Cham *et al.*, 2021; Ghosh, 2022; Moghavvemi *et al.*, 2021). This study's objective was to learn more about the adoption of m-wallets among India's millennials. Notably, most of our hypotheses have been well-supported. Largely, our findings show that a variety of benefits offered by m-wallet companies do tend to have a favorable influence on consumers' ATMW, which leads to a positive impact on the consumers' intention to them.

A detailed discussion on the hypotheses follows. Hypothesis H_1 is where in TA was found to be negatively associated with the ATMW. The findings did not support this hypothesis, and also differed from findings of a few earlier studies on m-wallets (Gelbrich and Sattler, 2014; Yang and Forney, 2013). It may be noted herein that a consumer faces anxiety due to his/her lack of knowledge and understanding of technology (Yang and Forney, 2013; Gao *et al.*, 2015). However, through our research, we noted that it was an insignificant factor, as our focus was on millennials, who are more 'tech-saavy' and thus, more open to adopt technology. They already use other forms of online payment mediums, like credit cards and online banking, and hence, are more comfortable in transacting online through technology. Therein, consumers did not feel anxious in using technology, given that they had prior experience (Deng *et al.*, 2014; Suarez *et al.*, 2019; Ooi *et al.*, 2020).

The hypothesis H_2 suggested that EE positively influences the consumers' attitude to use m-wallet for financial transactions. However, our results showed that EE for existing users with relatively new technologies, such as m-wallets applications are equally crucial to keep consumers interested and involved via an easy-to-use interface, in order to shape a positive individuals' ATMW.

Hypothesis H_3 suggested that SI would positively influence ATMW. Herein, it may be noted that our results concur with past literature, whereby it is shown that SI does have an impact on ATMW (Slade *et al.*, 2015; Chawla and Joshi, 2019; Bommer *et al.*, 2022). Moreover, given the rising prominence of social media, we also need to understand that word of mouth (WoM) and social media do play a defining role in forming consumers' attitudes. M-wallet companies should thereby focus on enhancing positive WoM related to m-wallets.

Next H_4 suggested that FC would positively influence ATMW. The findings of the study also support this argument. M-wallets companies should thereby focus on supportive applications in all smartphones. Importantly, these apps should be supportive even in low internet bandwidth also. It becomes important for mobile wallet companies to understand that the payments should be smooth and error free.

Hypothesis H_5 suggested that rewards positively influence ATMW. The findings support this hypothesis. This implies that rewards do impact the adoption of m-wallets. It can further be said that consumers are inclined

towards getting promotional benefits by making financial transactions through (Ly *et al.*, 2022). This trend can be noticed by Google Pay, whereby they started giving cashback on every transaction made, because of which customers were able to earn extra money (Malik and Annuar, 2021). Thus, this becomes extremely relevant in order to stay competitive.

Lastly, hypothesis H₆ suggested that ATMW would positively influence the individuals' BI to use m-wallets. Furthermore, it may be noted that consumers' ATMW came out as a strong antecedent in determining, especially the Indian millennial's intent to use m-wallets. The meta-UTAUT model's emphasis on 'attitude' as a conceptual framework for understanding specific technologies is furthered by this finding. Notably, this finding concurs with a few previous studies dealing with TRA (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1975) and TPB (Ajzen, 1991). Thus, m-wallet companies should focus on building a positive ATMW. This, in turn, would result in rise in consumers' intention to use them more extensively, especially for transacting online. Further, in order to remain competitive, it is extremely crucial for m-wallet companies to both identify and fulfill consumers' demands, and thereby develop a system that would fulfill the need.

CONTRIBUTION TO THEORY AND PRACTICE

Theoretical Implications

UTAUT model extension is the study's key theoretical contribution. The study even contributed to m-wallet literature. In various aspects, this research has updated India's millennials' intentions to adopt m-wallets. In fact, the empirical findings add to extant research, particularly on millennials' use of m-wallets. Secondly, it focused on the importance of rewards in the form of cashback and coupons for pushing consumers to adopt m-wallets. The results suggest that rewards should be considered as one of the constructs. In addition, technological anxiety is an important factor in determining the attitude of the consumer to consume a given technology has been added as a construct. In case of consumers' intent to use a new technology, it becomes important to understand the level of frustration or anxiety associated with it. Thirdly, we have added attitude as a variable to better understand the intention of the consumer to use mobile wallets. These factors provide richness to the UTAUT model and provide an explanation for critical variables determining adoption.

Practical Implications

This research also would possibly help business practitioners in terms of understanding consumers' attitudes related to the adoption of m-wallet. Based upon which, they could look to segment consumers, and position their strategies and policies accordingly, especially the millennial populous. Marketers on the other hand, may look to segment the millennial, and accordingly design business promotional ideas for them. As per the findings, reward plays a crucial role in the adoption of mobile wallet. In order to increase the stickiness to the mobile wallet, companies can offer different coupons, cashback, incentives etc. policymakers, local governments, and marketers may want to utilize the study's results to develop effective programs and tactics to encourage people to adopt m-wallets.

For business practitioners, a less difficult system with a reasonable transaction time might generate a favorable attitude toward mobile payments, thereby promoting its use. To be more specific, millennials can be explained the perks of using a mobile wallet for payments, for instance, they do not have to carry a physical wallet/purse and can benefit from a quicker checkout process. The advertisements should be made to demonstrate the use of mobile wallets and how a transaction might be completed successfully. Additionally, information regarding the benefits of using mobile wallets as opposed to alternative payment methods can be presented through the use of advertising. For example, the benefit of not having to carry a wallet or purse in order to keep plastic payment cards or cash, in conjunction with the requirement of only needing to carry a

single item that is one smartphone.

In addition, prospective adopters need to be made aware that infrastructure for mobile wallets are already available or widespread in India. The awareness can be created about this method of payment through merchants. The merchants can display banners or posters at the payment counters to let customers know that mobile wallet payments are accepted for payment purposes. This awareness can help promote perceptions of suitable benefits, which in turn can influence individuals' intentions regarding the use of mobile wallets. In addition, Indian millennials believe that in some places merchants prefer cash for payments, discouraging the use of mobile wallets due to transactional cost involved in the transfer of payment to the bank accounts. The solution for this problem is for practitioners to encourage more merchants to install payment terminals that are enabled for NFC. There is a potential for the establishment of incentive schemes to encourage the adoption and implementation of these terminals.

DIRECTION FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Though this research has theoretical and practical implications, however there are a few limitations to this study. For one, it has looked at India's Gen Y, which is a small portion of the country's entire population. Future research may examine different age groups' influence on m-wallet adoption. Scholars can examine the adoption from the senior citizen's point of view and can do a comparative study. This will give a broader image of the adoption behavior of mobile wallet. Second, future studies could possibly encompass a larger sample size with different demographics, incomes and cultures, which may yield interesting insights. Researchers can do cross-cultural research and even do a comparative study between emerging and developed economies to get a holistic image of mobile wallet ecosystem. Additionally, future studies may also consider including other variables, like consumers' habit, risks, experience vis a vis their impact on m-wallets real usage. Furthermore, a research can be conducted to gain insights in to the customer experience that will enable the mobile wallet service providers to provide better services and increase the loyalty towards the brand.

References: -

- Adeola, O., Moradeyo, A.A., Muogboh, O. and Adisa, I. (2021), "Consumer values, online purchase behaviour and the fashion industry: an emerging market context", PSU Research Review, Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Ajzen, I. (1991), "The theory of planned behavior", Elsevier, Vol. 50.
- Ajzen, I. and Fishbein, M. (1975), "A Bayesian analysis of attribution processes.", Psychological Bulletin, American Psychological Association, Vol. 82 No. 2, p. 261.
- Alalwan, A.A., Dwivedi, Y.K. and Rana, N.P. (2017), "Factors influencing adoption of mobile banking by Jordanian bank customers: Extending UTAUT2 with trust", International Journal of Information Management, Elsevier, Vol. 37 No. 3, pp. 99–110.
- Alalwan, A.A., Dwivedi, Y.K., Rana, N.P. and Williams, M.D. (2016), "Consumer adoption of mobile banking in Jordan: Examining the role of usefulness, ease of use, perceived risk and self-efficacy", Journal of Enterprise Information Management, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, Vol. 29 No. 1, pp. 118-139
- Alam, M.Z., Hu, W., Hoque, M.R. and Kaium, M.A. (2020), "Adoption intention and usage behavior of mHealth services in Bangladesh and China: A cross-country analysis", International Journal of

Pharmaceutical and Healthcare Marketing, Emerald Publishing Limited, Vol. 14 No. 1, pp. 37-60

- Baccarella, C.V., Wagner, T.F., Scheiner, C.W., Maier, L. and Voigt, K.-I. (2020), "Investigating consumer acceptance of autonomous technologies: the case of self-driving automobiles", *European Journal of Innovation Management*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Vol. 24 No. 4, pp. 1210-1232.
- Bailey, A.A., Pentina, I., Mishra, A.S. and Mimoun, M.S.B. (2017), "Mobile payments adoption by US consumers: an extended TAM", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Vol. 45 No. 6, pp. 626-640.
- Baptista, G. and Oliveira, T. (2015), "Understanding mobile banking: The unified theory of acceptance and use of technology combined with cultural moderators", *Computers in Human Behavior*, Elsevier, Vol. 50, pp. 418–430.
- Bhatia, C. (2020), "Millennials & Digital Payments | Here's How Millennials are Reshaping the Digital Payments Ecosystem", available at: <https://corp.ezetap.com/blogs/how-millennials-are-reshaping-the-digital-payments-ecosystem> (accessed 5 August 2022).
- Bommer, W.H., Rana, S. and Milevoj, E. (2022), "A meta-analysis of eWallet adoption using the UTAUT model", *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Vol. 40 No. 4, pp. 791-819.
- Boon, L.K., Fern, Y.S. and Fen, L.C. (2021), "Adoption of Mobile Wallet During Covid-19 Outbreak: The Consumer Perspective", *Journal of International Business, Economics and Entrepreneurship*, Vol. 6 No. 2, pp. 27–35.
- Brem, A., Viardot, E. and Nylund, P.A. (2021), "Implications of the coronavirus (COVID-19) outbreak for innovation: Which technologies will improve our lives?", *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, Elsevier, Vol. 163, p. 120451.
- Cham, T.-H., Cheah, J.-H., Cheng, B.-L. and Lim, X.-J. (2021), "I Am too old for this! Barriers contributing to the non-adoption of mobile payment", *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Vol. 40 No. 5, pp. 1017-1050.
- Chawla, D. and Joshi, H. (2019), "Consumer attitude and intention to adopt mobile wallet in India—An empirical study", *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Vol. 37 No. 7, pp. 1590-1618.
- Chawla, D. and Joshi, H. (2021), "Degree of awareness and the antecedents of the digital media platform: The case of mobile wallets", *FIIB Business Review*, SAGE Publications Sage India: New Delhi, India, p. 23197145211023412.
- Chen, Y.-S. and Chang, C.-H. (2013), "Greenwash and green trust: The mediation effects of green consumer confusion and green perceived risk", *Journal of Business Ethics*, Springer, Vol. 114 No. 3, pp. 489–500.
- Do, N., Tham, J., Khatibi, A. and Azam, S. (2019), "An empirical analysis of Cambodian behavior intention towards mobile payment", *Management Science Letters*, Vol. 9 No. 12, pp. 1941–1954.
- Dwivedi, Y.K., Rana, N.P., Jeyaraj, A., Clement, M. and Williams, M.D. (2019), "Re-examining the

unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT): Towards a revised theoretical model”, *Information Systems Frontiers*, Springer, Vol. 21 No. 3, pp. 719–734.

- Featherman, M.S. and Pavlou, P.A. (2003), “Predicting e-services adoption: a perceived risk facets perspective”, *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, Elsevier, Vol. 59 No. 4, pp. 451–474.
- FICCI economic outlook survey. (2022), “India’s GDP to Grow 7.4% in 2022-23: FICCI Economic Outlook Survey”, *News18*, 4 April, available at: <https://www.news18.com/news/business/indias-gdp-to-grow-7-4-in-2022-23-ficci-economic-outlook-survey-4937879.html> (accessed 5 August 2022).
- FIS Global. (2021), “Generation Pay Millennial payment trends - Insights | Worldpay from FIS”, available at: <https://www.fisglobal.com/en/insights/merchant-solutions-worldpay/article/generation-pay-millennial-payment-trends> (accessed 5 August 2022).
- Gao, Y., Li, H. and Luo, Y. (2015), “An empirical study of wearable technology acceptance in healthcare”, *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, Vol. 115 No. 9, pp. 1704-1723.
- Garrouch, K. (2021), “Does the reputation of the provider matter? A model explaining the continuance intention of mobile wallet applications”, *Journal of Decision Systems*, Taylor & Francis, Vol. 30 No. 2–3, pp. 150–171.
- Gelbrich, K. and Sattler, B. (2014), “Anxiety, crowding, and time pressure in public self-service technology acceptance”, *Journal of Services Marketing*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, Vol. 28 No. 1, pp. 82-94.
- George, A. and Sunny, P. (2021), “Developing a research model for mobile wallet adoption and usage”, *IIM Kozhikode Society & Management Review*, SAGE Publications Sage India: New Delhi, India, Vol. 10 No. 1, pp. 82–98.
- Ghosh, M. (2022), “Empirical study on consumers’ reluctance to mobile payments in a developing economy”, *Journal of Science and Technology Policy Management*, Emerald Publishing Limited..
- Glasheen, J. (2019), “Popular payment methods for millennial customers - ThePaypers”, available at: <https://thepayers.com/expert-opinion/popular-payment-methods-for-millennial-customers--781031> (accessed 5 August 2022).
- Global payment. (2022), “How Millennials and Gen Z are shaping the future of payments | Global Payments”, available at: <https://www.globalpayments.com/insights/2022/01/31/millennials-and-gen-z-shaping-the-future-of-payments> (accessed 5 August 2022).
- Gupta, A., Dogra, N. and George, B. (2018), “What determines tourist adoption of smartphone apps? An analysis based on the UTAUT-2 framework”, *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Vol. 9 No. 1, pp. 50–64.
- Hair, J.F., Ringle, C.M. and Sarstedt, M. (2011), “PLS-SEM: Indeed a silver bullet”, *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, Taylor & Francis, Vol. 19 No. 2, pp. 139–152.
- Kaur, P., Dhir, A., Bodhi, R., Singh, T. and Almotairi, M. (2020), “Why do people use and recommend m-wallets?”, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Elsevier, Vol. 56, p. 102091.

- Kim, Y.J. and Han, J. (2014), “Why smartphone advertising attracts customers: A model of Web advertising, flow, and personalization”, *Computers in Human Behavior*, Elsevier, Vol. 33, pp. 256–269.
- Kumar, R., Ratra, V. and Mandava, S. (2022), “Mobile wallet payments in the time of COVID-19: The Indian experience”, *Journal of Payments Strategy & Systems*, Henry Stewart Publications, Vol. 16 No. 1, pp. 7–16.
- Leong, L.-Y., Hew, T.-S., Ooi, K.-B. and Wei, J. (2020), “Predicting mobile wallet resistance: A two-staged structural equation modeling-artificial neural network approach”, *International Journal of Information Management*, Elsevier, Vol. 51, p. 102047.
- Lew, S., Tan, G.W.-H., Loh, X.-M., Hew, J.-J. and Ooi, K.-B. (2020), “The disruptive mobile wallet in the hospitality industry: An extended mobile technology acceptance model”, *Technology in Society*, Elsevier, Vol. 63, p. 101430.
- Liljander, V., Gillberg, F., Gummerus, J. and Van Riel, A. (2006), “Technology readiness and the evaluation and adoption of self-service technologies”, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Elsevier, Vol. 13 No. 3, pp. 177–191.
- Ly, H.T.N., Khuong, N.V. and Son, T.H. (2022), “Determinants Affect Mobile Wallet Continuous Usage in Covid 19 Pandemic: Evidence From Vietnam”, *Cogent Business & Management*, Taylor & Francis, Vol. 9 No. 1, p. 2041792.
- Madan, K. and Yadav, R. (2016), “Behavioural intention to adopt mobile wallet: a developing country perspective”, *Journal of Indian Business Research*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, Vol. 8 No. 3, pp. 227-244.
- Malik, A., Suresh, S. and Sharma, S. (2019), “An empirical study of factors influencing consumers’ attitude towards adoption of wallet apps”, *International Journal of Management Practice*, Inderscience Publishers (IEL), Vol. 12 No. 4, pp. 426–442.
- Malik, A.N.A. and Annuar, S.N.S. (2021), “The effect of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, reward, and perceived risk toward e-wallet usage intention”, *Eurasian Business and Economics Perspectives*, Springer, pp. 115–130.
- Mater, W., Matar, N., Alismaiel, O.A., Al Moteri, M.A., Al Youssef, I.Y. and Al-Rahmi, W.M. (2021), “Factors influencing the intention behind mobile wallet adoption: perceptions of university students”, *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, Vol. 9 No. 1, p. 447.
- Musleh, J.S., Marthandan, G. and Aziz, N. (2015), “An extension of UTAUT model for Palestine e-commerce”, *International Journal of Electronic Business*, Inderscience Publishers, Vol. 12 No. 1, pp. 95–115.
- Nunally, J.C. and Bernstein, I.H. (1978), “Psychometric theory”, New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Oliveira, T., Faria, M., Thomas, M.A. and Popovič, A. (2014), “Extending the understanding of mobile banking adoption: When UTAUT meets TTF and ITM”, *International Journal of Information Management*, Elsevier, Vol. 34 No. 5, pp. 689–703.
- Oliveira, T., Thomas, M., Baptista, G. and Campos, F. (2016), “Mobile payment: Understanding the

determinants of customer adoption and intention to recommend the technology”, *Computers in Human Behavior*, Elsevier, Vol. 61, pp. 404–414.

- Ooi, K.-B., Foo, F.-E., Tan, G.W.-H., Hew, J.-J. and Leong, L.-Y. (2020), “Taxi within a grab? A gender-invariant model of mobile taxi adoption”, *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Vol. 121 No. 2, pp. 312-332.
- Parasuraman, A. (2000), “Technology Readiness Index (TRI) a multiple-item scale to measure readiness to embrace new technologies”, *Journal of Service Research*, Sage Publications Sage CA: Thousand Oaks, CA, Vol. 2 No. 4, pp. 307–320.
- Park, J., Ahn, J., Thavisay, T. and Ren, T. (2019), “Examining the role of anxiety and social influence in multi-benefits of mobile payment service”, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Elsevier, Vol. 47, pp. 140–149.
- Patil, P.P., Dwivedi, Y.K. and Rana, N.P. (2017), “Digital payments adoption: an analysis of literature”, *Springer*, pp. 61–70.
- PHUONG, N.N.D., LUAN, L.T., DONG, V.V. and KHANH, N.L.N. (2020), “Examining customers’ continuance intentions towards e-wallet usage: The emergence of mobile payment acceptance in Vietnam”, *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, Korea Distribution Science Association, Vol. 7 No. 9, pp. 505–516.
- Rigdon, E.E. (2012), “Rethinking partial least squares path modeling: In praise of simple methods”, *Long Range Planning*, Elsevier, Vol. 45 No. 5–6, pp. 341–358.
- Ringle, C., Da Silva, D. and Bido, D. (2015), “Structural equation modeling with the SmartPLS”, Bido, D., Da Silva, D., & Ringle, C. (2014). *Structural Equation Modeling with the Smartpls*. *Brazilian Journal Of Marketing*, Vol. 13 No. 2.
- Ryan, R.M. and Connell, J.P. (1989), “Perceived locus of causality and internalization: examining reasons for acting in two domains.”, *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, American Psychological Association, Vol. 57 No. 5, p. 749.
- Ryan, R.M. and Deci, E.L. (2000), “Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations: Classic definitions and new directions”, *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, Elsevier, Vol. 25 No. 1, pp. 54–67.
- Schierz, P.G., Schilke, O. and Wirtz, B.W. (2010), “Understanding consumer acceptance of mobile payment services: An empirical analysis”, *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, Elsevier, Vol. 9 No. 3, pp. 209–216.
- Shaikh, A.A., Glavee-Geo, R. and Karjaluo, H. (2021), “How relevant are risk perceptions, effort, and performance expectancy in mobile banking adoption?”, *Research Anthology on Securing Mobile Technologies and Applications*, IGI Global, pp. 692–716.
- Sharma, P. (2021), “The rise of the Indian millennial”, *The Times of India*, available at: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/voices/the-rise-of-the-indian-millennial/> (accessed 5 August 2022).
- Susanto, P., Hoque, M.E., Hashim, N.M.H.N., Shah, N.U. and Alam, M.N.A. (2020), “Moderating

effects of perceived risk on the determinants–outcome nexus of e-money behaviour”, *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Vol. 17 No. 2, pp. 530-549.

- Talwar, S., Talwar, M., Kaur, P., Singh, G. and Dhir, A. (2021), “Why have consumers opposed, postponed, and rejected Innovations during a pandemic? A Study of mobile payment Innovations”, *Australasian Journal of Information Systems*, Australian Computer Society, Vol. 25.
- Tandon, U. and Kiran, R. (2018), “Study on drivers of online shopping and significance of cash-on-delivery mode of payment on behavioural intention”, *International Journal of Electronic Business*, Inderscience Publishers (IEL), Vol. 14 No. 3, pp. 212–237.
- Tarhini, A., El-Masri, M., Ali, M. and Serrano, A. (2016), “Extending the UTAUT model to understand the customers’ acceptance and use of internet banking in Lebanon: A structural equation modeling approach”, *Information Technology & People*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, Vol. 29 No. 4, pp. 830-849.
- Thakur, R. (2013), “Customer adoption of mobile payment services by professionals across two cities in India: An empirical study using modified technology acceptance model”, *Business Perspectives and Research*, SAGE Publications Sage India: New Delhi, India, Vol. 1 No. 2, pp. 17–30.
- Thakur, R. and Srivastava, M. (2014), “Adoption readiness, personal innovativeness, perceived risk and usage intention across customer groups for mobile payment services in India”, *Internet Research*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, Vol. 24 No. 3, pp. 369-392.
- Tusyanah, T., Wahyudin, A. and Khafid, M. (2021), “Analyzing factors affecting the behavioral intention to use e-wallet with the UTAUT model with experience as moderating variable”, *Journal of Economic Education*, Vol. 10 No. 1, pp. 113–123.
- Upadhyay, N., Upadhyay, S., Abed, S.S. and Dwivedi, Y.K. (2022), “Consumer adoption of mobile payment services during COVID-19: Extending meta-UTAUT with perceived severity and self-efficacy”, *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Vol. 40 No. 5, pp. 960-991.
- Vallerand, R.J. (1997), “Toward a hierarchical model of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation”, *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, Vol. 29, Elsevier, pp. 271–360.
- Varnali, K., Yilmaz, C. and Toker, A. (2012), “Predictors of attitudinal and behavioral outcomes in mobile advertising: A field experiment”, *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, Elsevier, Vol. 11 No. 6, pp. 570–581.
- Venkatesh, V. (2000), “Determinants of perceived ease of use: Integrating control, intrinsic motivation, and emotion into the technology acceptance model”, *Information Systems Research*, Informs, Vol. 11 No. 4, pp. 342–365.
- Venkatesh, V. and Bala, H. (2008), “Technology acceptance model 3 and a research agenda on interventions”, *Decision Sciences*, Wiley Online Library, Vol. 39 No. 2, pp. 273–315.
- Wong, K.K.-K. (2013), “Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) techniques using SmartPLS”, *Marketing Bulletin*, Vol. 24 No. 1, pp. 1–32.
- Wulandari, N. (2017), “Cashless payment in tourism. An application of technology acceptance model”,

Journal of Environmental Management & Tourism, pp. 1550–1553.

- Yan, L.-Y., Tan, G.W.-H., Loh, X.-M., Hew, J.-J. and Ooi, K.-B. (2021), “QR code and mobile payment: The disruptive forces in retail”, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Elsevier, Vol. 58, p. 102300.
- Yang, K. and Forney, J.C. (2013), “The moderating role of consumer technology anxiety in mobile shopping adoption: differential effects of facilitating conditions and social influences”, *Journal of Electronic Commerce Research*, *Journal of Electronic Commerce Research*, Vol. 14 No. 4, p. 334.
- Zhong, S., Lomas, C. and Worth, T. (2021), “Understanding customers’ adoption of express delivery service for last-mile delivery in the UK”, *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*, Taylor & Francis, pp. 1–18.